

PRACTICAL STAGES OF USING CASE STUDY TECHNOLOGIES AND DIDACTIC TOOLS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article discusses the advantages of CASE study teaching technologies in the flipped classroom model. In turn, they consist of technical and software tools: smart manuals, and textbooks, expressed in the form of software for creating and distributing interactive and communicative electronic educational materials. The author focuses on using computers or smartphones where providing videos, podcasts, banks, digital platforms, applications, and websites that are productive in teaching English.

Keywords: CASE study, flipped classroom, problem-solving, student-oriented, critical thinking, teaching technology.

In recent years, the term CASE study has also been widely used in the social, economic, and medical fields. In the educational system, however, CASE study has become increasingly popular as teaching technology. CASE study teaching technology develops creative thinking as well as enhances critical thinking skills in students by analyzing a problem situation. Students seek answers to complex questions by relying on real-life events through case studies. Also, during the course of the lesson, students are required to combine and synthesize information to solve the problem. Because, in this, each student learns to reflect on them, while seeking solutions to global problems within their field.

Communicative exercise "**Problem-solving**". In this exercise, the teacher will tell the students about a problematic situation or situation and ask them a question about the following content in order to find a solution to that problem. (*My car needed repairs three times in the last three weeks, and the last one was more serious than every time. However, I do not have enough funds to buy a new car. How should I behave?*) Students, on the other hand, will have to give their advice in order to solve the problem that has been thrown in between. When working with groups, the most optimal is chosen by comparing the answers, and with the help of a group, a solution to the situation is found, and the winning group is determined. See Figure 1.1:

Figure 1.1. "Problem-solving" communicative exercise

At the next stage, the parameters of the key assignment must be determined by the teacher. These parameters are reflected in drawing 1.2:

Figure 1.2. Case study technology parameters

Consequently, the "Flipped classroom" approach, on the other hand, is considered popular with the young people of technology. Accordingly, based on the Flipped classroom model, we would like to recommend the introduction of CASE study teaching technology. Because, in teaching students at the productive level, the Flipped classroom model offers the use of video assignments, training based on case study Technology, and the type of student-oriented education used in problem-solving. "Flipped classroom" differs from the traditional type of education in two ways, including meanings such as reverse, overturned class, or equipped class model:

1) active and student-oriented learning activities instead of standard classes; 2) provide students with the opportunity to gain ideas and insights on the topic by listening to materials in video form or short audio in advance so that they can gain independent knowledge beyond the lesson. Usually, while the teacher explains a new topic at the beginning of the lesson, in addition, the student is content with an assignment so that he can work from an independent home. However, in such a situation, it is natural that difficulties arise between students. This is because students have different levels of knowledge and acceptance, which include problems such as lack of understanding, low attentiveness, and embarrassment to their peers who are above themselves.

The use of CASE study Technology in the "Flipped classroom" model gives positive results in various levels of student active participation. In this case, students independently study materials on a new topic before classes and then make discussions on the same topic and methods of solving problems during classes. It is known that video and audio tasks give more results when mastered in the form of independent homework. Students can also listen repeatedly or pause and record so that they can understand the video or audio material given beforehand. Kahn Academy of quality audio and video materials to enable students to pursue independent education (<http://www.khanacademy.org/>), Kahoot when creating a video, audio, picture, or slides for various presentations, and a question-and-answer quiz! We recommend putting it into practice by using tools such as the Camastasia program when creating a mobile application, a Google service when listening to audio podcasts, or a personal video.

You can see the application of CASE study Technology in the "Flipped classroom" model using the drawing below. 1.3-see drawing:

Figure 3.2. CASE study Technology in the " Flipped Classroom" model

In the drawing above, we want to show that educational platforms, which are aimed at the independent performance of students before and during the course of classes are convenient for them to carry out their collaborative activities more efficiently, are used in such areas as Kahn Academy, Plickers, and Mentimeter. When creating these didactic materials, we would like to introduce case study technology based on the Flipped classroom model using the above educational platforms using the example of one of the topics relevant today, "Extreme environmental issues" i.e. According to this, students begin by familiarizing themselves with thematic vocabulary and vocabulary given to the Kahn Academy platform so that they can thoroughly master the topic of "Extreme environmental issues" before class. They are then given to read small texts on the subject given in the close reading informational text section.

Lessons

- Building knowledge
- Close reading: informational text
- Close reading: fiction
- Applying vocabulary knowledge
- Reading for understanding: informational text; Antarctica
- Reading for understanding: informational text; The Arctic Circle

Close reading: informational text

Learn

- ▶ Summarizing nonfiction | Reading
- ▶ What language shows cause and effect? | Reading
- ▶ Interpreting text features | Reading
- ▶ Finding connections between ideas within a passage | Reading

Practice

- ▶ Extreme Environments: reading informational text; Extreme Weather around the World 3
4 questions [Practice](#)

Close reading: fiction

Learn

- ▶ Summarizing stories | Reading
- ▶ Understanding theme | Reading

Practice

- ▶ Extreme Environments: reading realistic fiction; The Adventures of Fisher 3
4 questions [Practice](#)

✕ **Extreme Environments: vocabulary; Extreme Weather around the World 3**

Read the passage, then answer the practice question.

Extreme Weather around the World

1. Have you ever heard someone complain about the weather? It's always either too hot, too cold, too wet, too dry, and so on. It seems that we only get a few days a year when the weather is "just right". But really, all of these complaints seem silly when thinking about the world's extreme climates.

Do 4 problems ○ ○ ○ ○

[Check](#)

✕ **Extreme Environments: vocabulary; Extreme Weather around the World 3**

Extremely Hot

2. Is the harsh, scorching heat making your sandals sweaty? Well, in Dallol, Ethiopia, your shoes could melt if you stand still for a few minutes. Dallol is officially the hottest inhabited place on Earth. It's part of a desert region that is below sea level. In addition, Dallol sits on top of a volcano. The intense heat evaporates most of the water that flows into the area, leaving large salt slabs behind. The Afar people of Dallol harvest this salt to sell at local markets.

Do 4 problems ○ ○ ○ ○

[Check](#)

× **Extreme Environments: vocabulary; Extreme Weather around the World 3**

Read the sentence from paragraph 5.

"Absorb this: in Mawsynram, India, it basically *always* rains."

Why do you think the author used the phrase absorb this in the sentence?

Choose 1 answer:

(A) to highlight the difference between dry climates and rainy climates

(B) as a playful way to let the reader know that they will be learning about heavy rainfall

(C) to compare sponges and umbrellas in Southeast Asia

(D) as a way to introduce the topic of climate change in a serious manner

Do 4 problems **Check**

Untitled Set **Add to Queue**

B I U H Graded Survey Duplicate Delete

Watch a video then answer the questions below.

(A) What is the worst consumers of electricity which heats the planet?

(B) What is the Sky Cool?

(C) What are advantages of Sky Cool to our environment?

(D) How is the Sky Cool works?

Video

- Edit Video
- Replace
- Copy YouTube Link
- Open in YouTube
- Remove

Learn about Plickers Pro Shuffle Choices Saved just now **What's New** **Feedback**

Untitled Set **Add to Queue**

B I U H Graded Survey Duplicate Delete

How in the Cape Town, South Africa reduce the heating during the summer month?

(A) painting roofs white color

(B) planting greens

GIF

Learn about Plickers Pro Shuffle Add Choice Saved just now **What's New** **Feedback**

The screenshot displays the Plickers Pro interface. At the top, there are navigation icons for Bold (B), Italic (I), Underline (U), and Highlight (H), along with a 'Graded' status indicator and a 'Survey' title. The main content area features a question: 'Which 4 aspects are mentioned in the video as a consequences of climate change?'. To the right of the question is a video thumbnail titled 'Causes and Effects of Climate Change' with a menu icon. The video thumbnail has three categories listed: WEATHER, FOOD, and HEALTH. Below the question are three multiple-choice options: A) animals, children, flora and fauna; B) oceans, weather, food and health (highlighted in green); and C) older people, creatures, economy and species. On the right side, there is a 'Video' panel with options: Edit Video, Replace, Copy YouTube Link, Open in YouTube, and Remove. At the bottom of the interface, there are controls for 'Shuffle', 'Add Choice', and a 'Saved just now' indicator, along with 'What's New' and 'Feedback' buttons.

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